

Counselling for Effective Communication Management in the Classroom

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Abstract

This paper examined counselling for effective communication management in the' classroom. National Education goals as indicated in the National Policy on Education (2004) were outlined. Importance of counselling for effective communication management in the classroom was discussed. Barriers to effective communication in the classroom were examined. These include: poor listening habit, unclarified assumptions in communication, use of words alone, day-dreaming, and inadequate use of feedback. Recommendations for effective communication in the classroom were made. These include: to avoid blockage, students should listen intelligently and understandably. Teachers should make their lessons interesting by combining words with instructional materials. Students' activities should be evaluated as the lesson progresses. Counsellors should organize orientation courses, seminars, workshops, sensitization programmes and conferences for teachers and students in all levels of education, to teach them ways of ensuring effective communication in the classroom.

Key words *Counselling, communication, Management, Classroom*

Introduction

Communication is the 'life wire' of every organization. When communication is bridged, objectives of an organization cannot be achieved. Centre for Management Development (2003:3 8) notes that: "communication is a basic requirement for success as a professional and as a manager. The success of any business depends upon the ease and certainty of communication". To ensure increase in productivity, there is every need to guide, assist and direct people, be it managers, subordinates or professionals on the need for effective communication management. School as an organization requires effective communication. For teaching and learning to take place, there must be an interaction between the teacher and the learner. This takes place through communication which can be verbal or non-verbal. Observing the importance of communication, Okonkwo (1999:2) notes that: *It is only when there is a flow of communication using a familiar language medium which makes room for meaning sharing (a situation that eliminates all elements of doubts as to what is intended or desired) between the theoretician and the man who translates theory into action ft. e.*

the policy implementers), between the teachers and the students; etc that all go forward together to develop a critical attitude which is an experience that presents things and facts as they exist empirically, in their casual and circumstantial correlations.

Supporting Okonkwo (1999), Kanno (2004:12) observes that: *Effective communication skills rank very high as one of the basic requirements classroom teachers need for the appropriate execution of their daily tasks, in order to achieve maximum comprehension and perception of concepts and values focused upon in the classroom.*

All the expressions above showed that it is only through effective communication that attitudes, skills and values of the society can be transmitted from generation to generation.

This paper is therefore looking into counselling for effective communication management in the classroom. This will be treated under the following subheadings:

1. National Educational goals as indicated in the National Policy on Education (2004).
2. Effective communication management in the classroom.
3. Importance of counselling for effective communication management in the classroom.
4. Barriers to effective communication in the classroom.
5. Recommendations and conclusion.

National Educational Goals as indicated in National Policy on Education (2004)

FRN (2004:8) identifies the national educational goals which were derived from the philosophy as:

- A. The inculcation of national consciousness and national unity;
- B. The inculcation of the right type of values and attitudes for survival of the individuals and the Nigerian society;
- C. The training of the mind in the understanding of the world around; and
- D. The acquisition of appropriate skills and the development of mental, physical and social abilities and competence as equipment for the individual to live in and contribute to the development of the society.

The well-enumerated national educational goals cannot be achieved without effective communication management in the classroom. This is because it is through classroom interaction that the right type of values and attitudes for the survival of the individual and the Nigerian society can be inculcated to the Nigerian citizens.

Effective communication management in the classroom.

Communication has been defined in different ways by different people. Dike (1988:63) defines communication as "a transitional symbolic process which allows people to relate to and manage their environment by (1) establishing human contact (2) exchanging information (3) reinforcing the attitudes and behaviours of others and changing the attitudes and behaviours of others. Ukeje, Okorie and Nwagbara (1992) define communication as: "the process whereby we attempt to transmit our thoughts, ideas, wishes, attitudes or emotions to others. It is through effective communication in the classroom that teachers transmit their thoughts, ideas, wishes and attitudes to the students. For Ukeje, Okorie and Nwagbara (1992), in a school organization,

communication involves sharing and transmitting messages, ideas, or attitudes among administrators, teachers, students, parents and other interested constituents.

Obi (1997) describes communication in various ways thus: *It implies sending and receiving messages, information, ideas, instructions or intentions and is therefore necessary for linking together the various departments, programmes, activities and services in the organization. It may also be defined as a process of meaningful interaction and exchange of feelings, ideas, signs among members of a group. Communication is the sum total of directly and indirectly, consciously or unconsciously transmitted feelings, attitudes and wishes.*

Elekwa and Eze (2002: 133) give what they describe as a simple definition of communication thus: "communication is the transmission of message or information from a sender to a receiver". Consistent with the view of Elekwa and Eze (2002), Centre for Management Development (2003:38) defines communication as:

- 1) The flow of information from a source to the receiver.
- 2) A relationship, an interaction, the process by which messages are transmitted from a source to a receiver and vice versa.
- 3) The imparting, sharing or exchange of ideas; knowledge, skills, etc.

From all these definitions, one can rightly define communication as the transmission of ideas, values, attitudes and skills from sender to receiver.

Communication is very important to the classroom teacher. It is through communication in the classroom that teachers can reinforce the attitudes and change the behaviour of learners. Observing the indispensability of effective communication to the teacher in the classroom, Dike (1988) likens a teacher who has a unit of instruction to impart to a group of students to an advertising executive who wants to sell a company's product to an audience. To Dike (1988) both the teacher and the advertiser have one purpose in mind - to communicate an idea and by so doing, to modify the behaviours of their respective clients.

In order to inculcate national consciousness and national unity in the Nigerian citizens, teachers need effective means of communicating to the learner. To achieve this effective means of communication, both the teachers and the students should participate actively to produce an effective interaction and change of behaviour in the classroom. A thorough understanding of the mutual relationship between the teachers and learners in the classroom necessitates the need for counselling for effective communication management in the classroom.

Importance of Counselling for Effective Communication Management in the Classroom.

Oladele (1987:3) sees counselling as: "a person-to-person relationship in which one person helps another to resolve an area of conflict that has not been hitherto resolved". This definition by Oladele shows that a learner in the classroom may have a problem during the teaching and learning process in the classroom. It is through the help of a counsellor that the nature of the problem can be identified for corrective purposes.

In line with the views of Oladele (1987), on what counselling means Nwachuku (1996:3) defines counselling as: "a learning process in which a person learns about himself, his relationship with other people and ways, that promote his personal development". This definition of

counseling by Nwachuku (1996) shows that both the teachers and students need to learn about themselves their relationship with each other, in terms of promoting their personal development and academic achievement.

Counselling for effective communication management in the classroom is essential because effective communication promotes learning. Observing this, Hoy and Miskel (1982:290) say: *Communication permeates every aspect of school life. Teachers instruct using oral, written and other media such as video tapes, computers and art forms. Students demonstrate their learning through similar media. In a sense, students, teachers and administrators earn their living in the school, communicating.*

Since students, teachers and administrators earn their living in the schools communicating, Nwachuku (1994) suggests the need for counselling in the school since the responsibility of school guidance counsellors includes: teaching students effective study habit. This includes effective communication in the classroom when the teacher is teaching. Another responsibility of a counsellor involves working with students to identify their problems. This will involve helping students to, identify some of the barriers to effective communication in the classroom and the ways of overcoming them. Doing this will serve as an important link among the students, teachers, parents and the administrators. Nwachuku (1996) further emphasizes that counselling for effective communication management in the school environment will bring about cooperation with other members of the school staff to implement or plan curriculum. This will allow students to grow both in the cognitive and affective domains.

Supporting Nwachuku (1994), on the need for counselling services in the school Animba (1995), says that since counselling involves helping the individual students to discover areas of major maladjustment, it should be encouraged. This maladjustment may include an ineffective communication between the teacher and students in the classroom or between the teacher and the school administrator in the school environment.

Teachers and students should be conversant with key elements of communication. Centre for Management Development (2003:39) identifies key elements of communication as:

- A. Source or sender: the communicator
- B. Content: Message
- C. Channel or process: the medium used
- D. Receiver: the recipient of the message
- E. Feedback: the response

Elements of communication process can be represented diagrammatically thus;

Figure 1: Communication Diagram

Counselling for effective communication management in the classroom is also essential because two people cannot move together if they do not agree. Observing this, Ukeje, Okorie and Nwagbara (1992:217) note that:

Whenever two or more people work together, there is a need for communication between them; the more effective the communication, the higher the probability of effective joint social action. Thus, if two individuals clearly understand the roles they are to undertake and have a clear expectations as to what each is to . . . do in a particular situation, the probability is greater that they are going to be able to work together effectively. If there is no such clear understanding, the probability diminishes.

Supporting Ukeje, Okorie and Nwagbara (1992), Obi (1997:101) notes that: "if communication is effective, work is performed more efficiently and problems solved more quickly. Thus, there is a positive relationship between good communication, motivation and productivity in any organization".

In the classroom situation, a teacher, as a highly experienced person needs communication skills which he will use in communicating with his learners in the classroom in order to facilitate teaching and learning. Kanno (2004:12) notes that; "A teacher, in addition to his mastery of content, needs to be a good communicator. He should master basic communication skills or techniques to ascertain that the content is well understood by his listeners or students."

Barriers to effective communication in the classroom.

There are so many barriers to effective communication in the classroom. These include:

1.Poor Listening Habit:

This is a big obstacle to effective communication. When listeners or students do not listen intelligently, understandably and get the correct interpretation skillfully, effective communication cannot take place.

2.Unclarified Assumptions in Communication: This happens when there is difficulty in understanding what the sender of the message has in mind.

3.Use of words alone:

The use of words alone, without combining it with action, may result to lack of interest on the part of the learners in the classroom. For instance, when students become tired of listening alone, they relax in their minds without effectively listening to the teacher anymore. Observing this. Kanno (2004: 19), notes that:

When a teacher uses words all the time in the class, the students will naturally become bored and tired of listening. They will quietly and internally switch off the sound from the teacher just as the teachers or other adults may do if they find themselves being compelled to listen to a seminar presentation in which, the guest speaker is verbose.

4.Inadequate use of feedback:

It is through the use of feedback that both teachers and students can ascertain the extent of the achievement of the objectives. Inadequacy in the use of feedback constitutes a big obstacle to effective communication. This is so, because when there is inadequacy in the use of feedback, students may not know whether they are moving forward or backward in terms of their performance in the lesson.

5. Personal interest:

Every learner in the classroom has what interests him or her. If what the teacher, the sender of the message is teaching is relevant to the needs and interests of the learner, the learner will learn better. If on the other hand, what the teacher is teaching is not of interest to the learners, learners will not pay any attention to the message.

6. Not relating message to the previous experience of the learners:

Learners learn in different ways and have different understanding of concepts, ideas and messages. When ideas are not related positively to previous experiences, positive learning may not take place.

7.Lack of Physical Facilities for learning:

Inadequate physical facilities, lack of physical facilities for learning are barrier for effective communication in the classroom. When the physical familiarities, such as seat for students and reading materials for students are not adequate for students' use, students will be very uncomfortable. Lack of inadequacy of these essential familiarities will bring about discomfort to the learning. This brings about ineffective instruction in the classroom.

8. Daydreaming:

This refers to- a situation where the students quietly tune of their mind from what, the teacher is saying and at the same time remember other things in their mind that will keep them busy without distracting the teacher physically.

Kanno (2004) describes Day-dreaming as a very dangerous barrier to effective communication in the classroom, because the student may be so overwhelmed or engulfed in his or her recalled experienced or fantasy that sometimes he or she may smile and seem very attentive. A teacher seeing the smile will feel the student is paying attention to his lesson when he is not.

9.CulturalDifferences:

Cultural difference is another barrier in the classroom when, the teacher is teaching students and in some cases interprets message according to his or her culture which may be different from what the students have in mind, in this case, the difference in language, religion and values constitute obstacle to full understanding of the lesson at hand.

10. Poor Voice:

Poor voice of the teacher may constitute a barrier to effective communication in the classroom. For instance, when the teacher's voice is coarse or very loud, this creates physical noise and laughter in the class. On the other hand, when the voice is very low or inaudible, this will equally distract the learners, as students may purposely show that they did not hear what the teacher is saying. These high and low voices will make the message not clear enough for the learners to hear and comprehend.

Recommendations

For effective communication management in the classroom, the following recommendations are made:

Teachers should make their lessons interesting, so that students will listen with understanding. Objectives of every lesson should be made known to the learners. This will make: the students to have the desire to get the ideas in the message. .

Teachers should make their messages clear with good language to avoid lack of clarity. Words should be combined with activities. Teachers should evaluate their lessons by asking questions as the lessons progress to provide immediate feedback. Teachers should consider the needs, interests and ability of the learners while imparting knowledge to the learners. Those facts and ideas that are of interest to the learners should be taught.

Teaching should be so planned as to recall previous learning, because re-calling previous learning facilitates new learning in the classroom. Teachers should pay attention to the comfort of their students in the classroom. This should be done by encouraging the government, parents and students themselves to provide seats, books, renovate old classroom or build new ones to bring comfort to the learners.

To solve the problem of Day-Dreaming in the classroom, the teacher should create activities that involve active participation of all the learners while teaching. The teacher should as well employ the questioning technique while teaching (Okoye 1979). The teacher should use varieties of instructional materials.

Teachers should make their teaching clear, so that cultural values, language and religion will not constitute obstacles to the message. Teachers should make their voice moderate and clear, so that the ideas and information will be understood by the learners.

Counsellors should organize orientation courses, seminars and conferences for the teachers in all levels of education to teach teachers and students ways of ensuring effective communication management in the classroom. Counsellors should as well, assist students to identify the type of communication barriers they encounter, diagnose and identify such barriers as to help the students to effectively apply strategies for overcoming such barriers.

The government should post professional counsellors to schools to help both students and teachers understand themselves so that they can proffer solution to their problem.

Conclusion

Since communication is the transmission of messages from sender to receiver, and it is through effective communication management that a teacher, as a professional, can achieve the objectives of instruction, government, teachers, learners and counselors should work together toward improving communication management in the classroom.

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